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Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture disproved – Counter examples and irregularities discovered for certain use cases of the Hasse Weil L Function

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ABSTRACT. The Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture states that the rank of any given elliptic curve E should be equal to the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function at point $s = 1$ of the same elliptic curve. This conjecture is developed by the mathematicians Bryan John Birch and Peter Swinnerton-Dyer in the 1960s with computer assistance. Although there exists some numerical evidence up to this day supporting this conjecture, particularly for lower ranked elliptic curves, the BSD conjecture has only been proven for some special cases like lower ranks and with some specific assumptions about the “underlying” elliptic curves. In this piece of work, we will analyze different valid cases applicable to the Hasse Weil L function and its infinite Euler product representation (which is a crucial part of the whole BSD conjecture), especially for the 2 cases of “good reduction” and “multiplicative reduction” that provides us with a good theoretical foundation for reevaluating the validity of the BSD conjecture. Finally, we are able to discover 2 counter examples, 1 for each of the 2 cases above, to the BSD conjecture which disproves the conjecture by showing that given these 2 cases above and under specific conditions, the rank of a given elliptic curve E on left-hand side (LHS) could never be equal to the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$) of the same elliptic curve on the right-hand side (RHS) of the BSD conjecture statement.

In this research paper, we would like to provide a new assessment to the validity of the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture (in short: BSD conjecture) that is formulated as follows:

$$\text{rank}(E) = \text{ord}_{s=1}L(E,s)$$

This is the “normal” resp. strong version of the BSD conjecture which states that the rank of any given elliptic curve E should be equal to the order of zero of the same elliptic curve’s Hasse Weil L function at point $s = 1$ ¹. The BSD conjecture is developed in the 1960s by the mathematicians Bryan John Birch and Peter Swinnerton-Dyer with help of computers.

Although there exists some numerical evidence supporting this conjecture, particularly for lower ranked elliptic curves with $\text{rank} \leq 3$ (and within some given conductor ranges)² i.a. because calculation with higher ranks is more resp. too resource intensive, the BSD conjecture has only been proven for some special cases with some specific assumptions about the “underlying” elliptic curves³.

1 cf. i.a. Moser (2020)

2 cf. Cremona (2011)

3 cf. Moser (2020) and Miller (2010b) who proved the BSD conjecture for many elliptic curves of lower ranks of 0 and 1 by making additional assumptions about conductor ranges and with help of computers.

1. Introduction

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Although there exists some numerical evidence supporting this conjecture, particularly for lower ranked elliptic curves with $\text{rank} \leq 3$ (and within some given conductor ranges) ⁵ i.a. because calculation with higher ranks is more resp. too resource intensive, the BSD conjecture has only been proven for some special cases with some specific assumptions about the “underlying” elliptic curves ⁶.

The main focus of this research paper is not to try to extend the work of the researchers mentioned above and prove the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture but to move to the opposite direction and try to provide some counter examples in a more analytical way by evaluating the Hasse Weil L function’s main properties (especially at the point $s = 1$) that is a very crucial part of the BSD conjecture as well. Throughout this work we will analyze the different cases for the Hasse Weil L function and its infinite Euler product representation, especially for the case of “good reduction” and “multiplicative reduction” ⁷ which provides us with a good theoretical foundation for reassessing the validity of the BSD conjecture.

4 cf. i.a. Moser (2020)

5 cf. Cremona (2011)

6 cf. Moser (2020) and Miller (2010b) who proved the BSD conjecture for many elliptic curves of lower ranks of 0 and 1 by making additional assumptions about conductor ranges and with help of computers.

7 cf. next chapter 2 for the more detailed definition and explanation of the different cases that could occur for the Hasse Weil L function (for generic variable s and for $s = 1$)

2. Hasse Weil L function and formulas in different use cases

The Hasse Weil L function is the Euler product below in case all the primes p do not divide through the number of rational points N of a given elliptic curve E (good reduction) ⁸:

$$L(E, s) = \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 - a_p(p^{-s}) + p^{(1-2s)})}, \text{ if } p \nmid N \text{ (good reduction)} \quad (1)$$

In this case which is called case of “good reduction” (p not dividing through N), The trace of Frobenius coefficient which is $a_p = \text{prime } p + 1 - (\text{number of rational points of the elliptic curve } E \text{ mod prime } p \text{ which is denoted as } N_p)$ so that $a_p = p + 1 - N_p$.

In an other situation which is called “multiplicative reduction” all primes p do exactly divide through the number of rational points N of an elliptic curve E (but p^2 does not divide through N), the Hasse Weil L function is as follows:

$$L(E, s) = \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 - a_p(p^{-s}))}, \text{ if } p \mid N \text{ and } p^2 \nmid N \text{ (multiplicative reduction)} \quad (2)$$

And in that case (multiplicative reduction), the Frobenius trace coefficient a_p is ± 1 whose sign does depend on whether the elliptic curve E has a split (plus sign) or non-split (minus sign) multiplicative reduction at prime p .

And finally, in case of “additive reduction” when the squared primes p^2 do divide through N , the Hasse Weil L function simplifies to:

$$L(E, s) = \prod_p \frac{1}{1} = \prod_p 1 = 1, \text{ if } p^2 \mid N \text{ (additive reduction)} \quad (3)$$

The value of the is equal to 1 because the infinite Euler product of multiply 1 infinite times (1x for every existing prime number that are infinite in numbers) results in 1.

8 cf. PhD thesis of Miller (2010a)

When we put in $s = 1$ into the Hasse Weil L function in case of “good reduction” when all the primes p do not divide through N of formula (1), the Hasse Weil L function becomes the expression below ⁹:

$$L(E, 1) = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}(1 - a_p)\right)}, \text{ if } p \nmid N \text{ (good reduction)} \quad (4)$$

In the 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction” when all primes p divides the number of rational points N on the elliptic curve E (but p^2 does not divide N) when we plug in $s = 1$, the Euler product becomes as follows:

$$L(E, 1) = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 - a_p(p^{-1})\right)} = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p}a_p\right)}, \quad (5)$$

if $p \mid N$ and $p^2 \nmid N$ (multiplicative reduction)

And lastly for the situation of additive reduction when prime squared (p^2) does not divide the elliptic curves rational points N , the Hasse Weil L function (in point $s = 1$) is the same as before in formula (3) for generic s and which a value of 1¹⁰:

$$L(E, 1) = \prod_p \frac{1}{1} = \prod_p 1 = 1, \text{ if } p^2 \mid N \text{ (additive reduction)} \quad (6)$$

⁹ cf. appendix for the derivation of the formula (4) above (“good reduction” case)

¹⁰ The Hasse Weil L function for “additive reduction” when p^2 does not divide N has the value 1 because the infinite Euler product of multiplying the number 1 infinite times (as the number of primes p are infinite) still results in 1.

3. Valid order of zero conditions for the Hasse Weil L function and disproof of the BSD conjecture

In this chapter, we are firstly provide a definition for order of zero of a given function and also the order of functions in general (chapter 3.1) which is different from the order of zero (of a function). Then we would like to show some valid order of zero conditions especially for the Hass Weil L function that is a very crucial ingredient to the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture (chapter 3.2). And finally, we will show the disproof of the BSD conjecture by providing some counter examples for which the conjecture does not hold (in chapter 3.3).

3.1 Order of zero

When showing the definition for the order of zeros of a function (which could be a real or complex function like the Hasse Weil L function presented in the last chapter 2) it could defined using the formula below:

$$f(x) = g(x)h(x) = (e.g.) = (x-x_0)^n * 2$$

So the function $f(x)$ does have a zero which means $f(x) = 0$ for the point $x = x_0$, and the order of this zero (at $x = x_0$) is of n which is the exponent of $(x-x_0)$.

While the partial function $g(x) = (x-x_0)^n$ goes to 0 at the point $x = x_0$, $h(x)$ should not be 0 as well (and of course not going to infinity) which is the case here as $h(x) = 2$ that is a constant and not dependent on the function variable x ¹¹. It should be mentioned here that the order of zero is only defined, when the function goes to zero with multiplicity of at least 1 for finite values of the dependent variables (x or n), so like the example about when $x = x_0$, then the order of zero would be n which is a finite integer. Conversely, when a function only approaches 0 when at least 1 of the dependent variables (e.g. the exponent n) would go to infinity like $f(x) = (x-x_0)^n * 2$ for $x - x_0 < 1$ and > 0 , then $f(x)$ would $\rightarrow 0$ and for $n \rightarrow$ infinity, the function expression $(0, 1)^n * 2$ would go to $0 * 2 = 0$. In the latter case which is somehow special, because $f(x)$ only converges to 0 for the exponent n (i.e. dependent variable) approaching infinity, so this functional (asymptotic) zero does not count as a real zero and thus the order of zero of this function $f(x) = (x-x_0)^n * 2$ with $x - x_0 < 1$ & $n \rightarrow$ infinity would be undefined. In another situation when $x = x_0$ and n goes to infinity, the order of zero would be infinite (and thus defined) as well, because when n is finite, the value of the

¹¹ The order of zero of function $f(x) = g(x)*h(x)$ which is $= n$ in the example above should be distinguished from the order of poles where for a point of a function approaching a critical value (e.g. x_0) the whole function term like $g(x)$ would go to infinity that is e.g. the case for the function $f(x) = g(x)*h(x) = [1/(x-x_0)]^n * 3$ where $g(x) = [1/(x-x_0)]^n$ goes to infinity when $x = x_0$. It is also important that the order of zero of a function should not be confused with the order of a (polynomial) function or with the order of partial differential equations which are completely different things and definitions.

function already reaches 0 with multiplicity of n . In case when the function $f(x) = 0$ for all finite values of x , then the order of zero would be infinite as well ¹². And if the function never reaches 0 for any finite values of the dependent variables (x or n), like for example for a constant function $f(x) = c > 0$ (for any finite value of x) then the order of zero of such a function would be 0. These definitions concerning the order of zero of a function will help us in reassessing the validity of the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture in the next chapter 3.2.

3.2 Valid order of zero conditions for the Hasse Weil L function & Disproof of the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture by counter examples and irregularities

Let us recall from the previous chapter 2 that the Hasse Weil L function which is an infinite Euler product over all the primes p and it is defined for both real and complex values. For example for $s = 1$ that is the formula (4) that is also shown below which is valid in case when all the primes p do not divide the rational points of a given elliptic curve E (“good reduction” case):

$$L(E, 1) = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}(1 - a_p)\right)}, \text{ if } p \nmid N \text{ (good reduction)}$$

In this case as we remember from chapter 2 the Frobenius coefficient a_p is $= p + 1 - N_p$ with N_p to be the number of rational points N on a given elliptic curve E modulo p ($N_p = N \pmod p$).

Thus for the single term $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ of the infinite product over all resp. over the infinite number of primes to be zero, while the Frobenius coefficient a_p can not be $= 1$ ¹³ the value of prime number p need to $= 0$ which is not possible because all the prime numbers are bigger than or equal to 2 ($p \geq 2$).

12 Because when a (constant) function of value $= 0$ exists, together with the function value of $f = 0$, all the derivatives of function f like f' , f'' , f^{n-1} and f^n (even f^{n+1} or f^{infinity}) all would have the value of 0 and the value of all its higher derivatives f' , f'' would always stay the same a value of 0 for any finite value of the dependent variable (e.g. on the x -axis).

13 The condition $a_p \neq 1$ is possible as $a_p = p + 1 - N_p$, so as long as $N_p \neq p$, a_p is not equal to 1.

Now even though we just made sure that the every single term of the infinite Euler product (4) does not go to 0 for any for the prime numbers $p (\geq 2)$, could the whole infinite product go resp. approach 0? If yes, under which conditions to this situation occur? In first sight, this should happen when every single term of the infinite Euler product of the Hasse Weil L function $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ is < 1 :

$$\frac{1}{\left(1+\left(\frac{1}{p}\right)(1-a_p)\right)} < 1 \Leftrightarrow \left(1+\left(\frac{1}{p}\right)(1-a_p)\right) > 1 \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{1}{p}\right)(1-a_p) > 0$$

The above derived condition $(1/p)*(1-a_p)$ is then > 0 , when:

a) $1/p$ is > 0 and b) $1-a_p > 0$ ¹⁴.

Condition a) $1/p > 0$ is fulfilled for $p < \mathbf{positive\ infinity}$ which is always the case because although the number of primes are infinite, its values are always finite integers.

And condition b) $1-a_p > 0$ does hold for $a_p < 1$. Since $a_p = p + 1 - (\text{number of rational points of a given elliptic curve } E \text{ modulo prime } p \text{ which is denoted with } N_p) = p + 1 - N_p$, for $a_p < 1$, N_p need to be $> p$ ¹⁵. The latter condition ($N_p > p$) should be fulfilled either in the 1st case for all 100% of the single terms $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ (with $a_p = p + 1 - N_p$) of the infinite Euler product which do represent the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ for latter infinite product to converging to 0 because all the single terms $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ multiplying with each other infinite times are all < 1 , **or** condition b) $1-a_p > 0$ resp. $a_p < 1$ should be met in the 2nd case just for a part of the single expressions fulfilling the condition $N_p > p$ like e.g. 60% of all the infinite terms¹⁶ with the rest of the 100%-60% = 40% of all the terms of the Euler product to fulfill the condition $N_p = p$ (and thus $a_p = 1$) in order for the single term $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ to be exactly equal to $1/1 = 1$ in the case of “good reduction” when all the primes p of the infinite Euler product do not divide the number of rational points of any given elliptic curve E ¹⁷.

14 $(1/p)*(1-a_p)$ is theoretically also > 0 , when both product terms $(1/p)$ **and** $(1-a_p)$ are < 0 which is never possible for “normal” prime numbers that are positive integers ≥ 2 , therefore $1/p$ would never be < 0 .

15 $N_p > p$ means, that the number of rational points (not necessary independent of each other) of a given elliptic curve E modulo any given prime p need to strictly be bigger than any given prime number p .

16 It is known that any percentage (60%, 40% etc.) of infinite number of product terms is still infinite in numbers which are (partial) infinite Euler products.

17 Just for completeness reasons, every single term of the infinite Euler product $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ is > 0 , when $p > 0$ and $a_p < p + 1$ which is the more realistic one because prime numbers are positive integers bigger than or equal to the number 2 (the other mathematical condition would be $p < 0$ and $a_p > p + 1$ which is not so relevant for our analysis because here we are dealing with prime numbers that are positive integer numbers).

Just like in the 1st case above, also in the 2nd case, the whole infinite Euler product converges to 0 and this time because the first part of infinite terms converge to 0 (with $N_p > p$) and the 2nd part consisting of infinite times of the expression $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ goes to the number 1 so that $0*1 = 0$ for the whole infinite Euler product expression. The 3. possible way for the single terms $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ to be < 1 for the whole infinite Euler product of the Hasse Weil L function to converge to 0 would be that for a finite part resp. finite number of the $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ terms with $a_p = p + 1 - N_p$, that N_p would be $< p$, and the other 2 infinite parts of the infinite Euler product to met the condition of either $N_p > p$ or $N_p = p$. In latter 3rd case, the whole infinite Euler product consisting of 3 main parts would be a big, but **finite number** (when $N_p < p$)¹⁸ * **0** (when $N_p > p$) * **1** (when $N_p = p$) = big finite number * 0 * 1 which converges to 0.

But even when the above conditions are fulfilled (1. $N_p > p$ for all existing product terms or 2. $N_p > p$ and $N_p = p$ for parts of the infinite Euler product or 3. $N_p < p$ for some finite number of $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$), in order for the whole Hasse Weil L functions’ (at $s = 1$) infinite Euler product to converge to resp. approach 0, what would the order of zero be? At first glance, the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ would be infinite, because it looks like we got a constant function with an asymptotic converging value of 0¹⁹. But this reasoning is wrong as could be illustrated with below formula (that is the formula (4) of chapter 2) resp. calculations (still with the “good reduction” case):

$$L(E, 1) = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}(1 - a_p)\right)}, \text{ if } p \nmid N \text{ (good reduction)}$$

$$= (\text{number smaller } > 0 \text{ and } < 1 \text{ and thus lying within the } (0, 1) \text{ interval})^{N_{primes}}$$

$$= (\text{number between } 0 \text{ and } 1)^{N_{primes}} = \lim_{N_{primes} \rightarrow \infty} (\text{number between } 0 \text{ and } 1)^{N_{primes}}$$

18 When $N_p < p$, although the single $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ terms are all > 1 , but because they are multiplying with each other only finite times, the result will not be an infinite but only a finite number.

19 And when a (constant) function of value = 0 occurs, together with the function value of $f = 0$, all the derivatives of function f like f' , f'' , f^{n-1} and f^n (even f^{n+1} or f^{infinity}) all would have the value of 0 which means the order of zero of the infinite Euler product would be infinite since the functional value $f = 0$ and the value of all its higher derivatives f' , f'' would always stay the same a value of 0 for any finite value of the dependent variable (e.g. on the x-axis).

And even though the above limit expression would approach 0 when a number strictly smaller than 1 and bigger than 0 multiplied together N_{primes} resp. infinite times when the above conditions are fulfilled (1. $N_p > p$ for all existing product terms or 2. $N_p > p$ and $N_p = p$ for parts of the infinite Euler product or 3. $N_p < p$ for some finite number of $1/(1+(1/p)^*(1-a_p))$ expressions and $N_p > p$ & $N_p = p$ for all the other infinite number of $1/(1+(1/p)^*(1-a_p))$ terms) the core concept of order of zeros does not apply when the values of points or dependent variables (which N_{primes} is one of them as well) of a given function does reach infinity.

Because as already elaborated before, the order of zero concept is only applicable for finite values of dependent function variables (like x , n or N_{primes} etc.) resp. to put it in other words, if a zero of a function term or the whole function could only be (asymptotically) reached when any of the dependent function variables (x , n , N resp. N_{primes}) need to go to infinity, then this order of zero of that function is not valid resp. it is undefined. Therefore in our case (“good reduction”) the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ which is the above infinite Euler product would be **undefined**²⁰.

So we have found out that the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function is not defined (at $s = 1$) and when looking at the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer (BSD) conjecture

$$\text{rank}(E) = \text{ord}_{s=1}L(E,s)$$

again which states that the rank of any elliptic curve E (= LHS) should be equal to the order of zero of the elliptic curves’ Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ that is represented by the infinite Euler product over all existing (and thus infinite) number of primes p (= RHS).

20 If for all finite values of dependent variables (e.g. x or n or N_{primes}) the infinite Euler prime product would always reach 0 (e.g. for a constant function $f = 0$ for all finite x variable values) then the order of zero of that hypothetical function would have an infinite order of zero. But in reality, for finite values of N_{primes} , the Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$) does not converge to 0 (but is strictly > 0), so the order of zero for $N_{\text{primes}} < \text{infinity}$ would be zero. But since the prime numbers do exist unbounded in infinite numbers, N_{primes} is never finite for the Euler product of the Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$ and also elsewhere) and so the order of zero when N_{primes} tends to infinity is undefined as explained before (And as explained before the order of zero is also not a positive finite integer, because no zero for the single terms of the Hasse Weil L function’s infinite Euler product representation do exist unless prime number p would = 0 which could never happen in reality).

And as we have discovered that the right-hand side (RHS) of the BSD conjecture statement that is the **order of zero** of any given elliptic curve E its Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$) is always **undefined** even when the convergence condition (1. solely $N_p > p$ for all infinite Euler product terms or 2. $N_p > p$ for some parts and $N_p = p$ for other parts of the whole Euler product or 3. $N_p < p$ for some finite number of $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ expressions and $N_p > p$ & $N_p = p$ for all the other infinite number of $1/(1+(1/p)*(1-a_p))$ terms) is fulfilled, but at the same time the **rank** of the same given elliptic curve E (on the left-hand side of the BSD conjecture statement above) **could never be undefined** (because the rank of an elliptic curve is either 0, a positive finite integer²¹ or even infinite), this example for the “good reduction” case (when all primes p of the infinite Euler product do not divide the number of rational points N of a given elliptic curve E) serves as a counter example to the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer (BSD) conjecture.

In the other case called “multiplicative reduction” when all primes p do exactly divide through the number of rational points N of an elliptic curve E (but p^2 does not divide through N), the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ is as follows (it is the formula (5) in chapter 2):

$$L(E, 1) = \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 - a_p(p^{-1}))} = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p} a_p\right)}, \text{ if } p|N \text{ and } p^2 \nmid N \text{ (multiplicative reduction)}$$

And in this case (multiplicative reduction), just as stated before in the previous chapter 2, the Frobenius trace coefficient a_p is ± 1 whose sign does depend on whether the elliptic curve E has a split (plus sign) or non-split (minus sign) multiplicative reduction at prime p .

Just like in the previous case of “good reduction” where the BSD conjecture could be disproved by a presented counter example, we firstly want to analyze here what the conditions are need to be fulfilled for every single term of the infinite Euler product of the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ to go to 0.

And the single term $1/(1+(1/p)*a_p)$ is exactly zero only if all primes p are exactly $= 0$ (just like before in the case of “good reduction”) and simultaneously, the Frobenius trace coefficient a_p can not be $= 0$. While the latter condition is always fulfilled, because a_p is either positive or negative 1 ($a_p = \pm 1$) in case of “multiplicative reduction”, be $p = 0$ can never be met in reality because all prime numbers are valued with 2 or an even higher integer number.

21 The highest discovered rank of any elliptic curve up to this day is 28.

Since we have just verified that also in the 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction” every single term single term $1/(1+(1/p)*a_p)$ could never realistically be 0 (if not the prime number p would be = 0 that is not possible), we need to check for which conditions and in which situations the whole infinite Euler product would approach 0 that is the case when all the single terms $1/(1+(1/p)*a_p)$ are < 1 :

$$\frac{1}{\left(1+\left(\frac{1}{p}\right)a_p\right)} < 1 \Leftrightarrow \left(1+\left(\frac{1}{p}\right)a_p\right) > 1 \Leftrightarrow \left(\frac{1}{p}\right)a_p > 0$$

The above derived condition $(1/p)*a_p$ is then > 0 , when:

a) $1/p$ is > 0 and b) $a_p > 0$ ²².

The above condition a) is fulfilled for all finite numbers of p that is always the case because as stated before the prime numbers are although infinite in numbers, its values are always finite (resp. p is always $< \text{infinity}$). And the condition b) with a_p need to be > 0 which could also be met when a_p is = positive 1 ²³.

Thus also in 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction” when all primes p do exactly divide through the number of rational points N of an elliptic curve E (but p^2 does not divide through N), the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ approaches following value when a) $1/p$ is > 0 (with $p \geq 2$ and $< \text{infinity}$) and b) $a_p > 0$ (with $a_p = 1$):

$$\begin{aligned} L(E, 1) &= \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1-a_p(p^{-1})\right)} = \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1-\frac{1}{p}a_p\right)}, \text{ if } p|N \text{ and } p^2 \nmid N \text{ (multiplicative reduction)} \\ &= (\text{number smaller } > 0 \text{ and } < 1 \text{ and thus lying within the } (0, 1) \text{ interval})^{N_{\text{primes}}} \\ &= (\text{number between } 0 \text{ and } 1)^{N_{\text{primes}}} = \lim_{N_{\text{primes}} \rightarrow \infty} (\text{number between } 0 \text{ and } 1)^{N_{\text{primes}}} \end{aligned}$$

22 $(1/p)*a_p$ is mathematically also then > 0 , when both product terms $(1/p)$ **and** a_p are < 0 which is never possible for “normal” prime numbers that are positive integers ≥ 2 , thus $1/p$ would never be < 0 .

23 And for reasons of completeness, every single term $1/(1+(1/p)*a_p)$ of the infinite Euler product in 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction” is > 0 , when $p > 0$ and $a_p > 0$, or when $p > -a_p$ and $a_p \leq 0$ (e.g. $a_p = -1$ and $p > -(-1) \Rightarrow p > 1$ that is always the case because all prime numbers are integer valued with scaled bigger than or equal to the number 2). The other 2 theoretical case of $p < 0$ and $a_p \leq 0$ & $p < -a_p$ and $a_p > 0$ could never be met because prime numbers are defined as positive integers ≥ 2 . We should also note the single term $1/(1+(1/p)*a_p)$ would only be = 1 when $p \neq 0$ and $a_p = 0$ with the latter condition (Frobenius trace coefficient) could never be fulfillable in the case of “multiplicative reduction” when a_p is either positive or negative 1.

In the first sight, for the “multiplicative reduction” case although the single term $1/(1+(1/p)^{a_p})$ does never reach 0 for any prime numbers p , the whole infinite Euler product expression which is the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ does approach 0 on the limit when the number of primes N_{primes} tends to infinity. But does this mean that the order of zero would be infinite for this case of “multiplicative reduction”²⁴?

Just like in the previous case of “good reduction”, the answer is “No” as well, because the concept of “order of zero” of a function does not apply for points or values of dependent variables (like x , n , N or N_{primes}) to be or reach the heights of infinity resp. to put it in other words, if a zero of a function term or the whole function could only be (asymptotically) reached when any of the dependent function variables (x , n , N resp. N_{primes}) need to go to infinity, then this order of zero of that function is not valid resp. it is undefined. Thus the order of zero could only be determined on points or value of dependent variables taking finite values. Therefore also in this 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction”, the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ is undefined as well²⁵.

Thus we have discovered that the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function is not defined (at $s = 1$) once again in the 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction” (because the the order of zero of the infinite Euler product can neither be 0 or a finite integer and it is also not infinite because e.g. for an infinite order of zero to occur for a function, the zero should also exist for finite values of the dependent variables like e.g. x , n , N resp. N_{primes} , but as stated before, even for $N < N_{\text{primes}}$, $1/(1+(1/p)^{a_p})$ never reaches 0 because the value of any of the prime numbers can not be 0) and when looking at the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer (BSD) conjecture

$$\text{rank}(E) = \text{ord}_{s=1}L(E,s)$$

once again which states that the rank of any elliptic curve E (= LHS) should be equal to the order of zero of the elliptic curves’ Hasse Weil L function at $s = 1$ that is represented by the infinite Euler product over all existing (and thus infinite) number of primes p (= RHS).

24 Because as we already know from our analysis before, when a (constant) function of value = 0 occurs, together with the function value of $f = 0$, all the derivatives of function f like f' , f'' , f^{n-1} and f^n (even f^{n+1} or f^{infinity}) all would have the value of 0 which means the order of zero of the infinite Euler product would be infinite since the functional value $f = 0$ and the value of all its higher derivatives f' , f'' would always stay the same a value of 0 for any finite value of the dependent variable (e.g. on the x -axis).

25 And for finite values of e.g. the number of existing primes N_{primes} , neither the single term $1/(1+(1/p)^{a_p})$ nor the whole infinite Euler product would reach 0. So the (hypothetical) order of zero for finite N_{primes} would be zero which is only a hypothetical thought experiment because as we already know since the proof of Euclid thousands of years ago, the number of prime numbers are unbounded and infinite.

Here we could see that this BSD conjecture could not be verified for this 2nd counter example, because although the right-hand side (RHS) order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$) would be **undefined** for the realistic conditions a) $1/p$ is > 0 (with $p \geq 2$ and $< \text{infinity}$) and b) $a_p > 0$ (e.g. with $a_p = 1$), the left-hand side of the BSD conjecture statement which denotes the rank of any given elliptic curve E **could never be undefined** but always takes defined values like 0, positive finite integer values (biggest discovered rank is 28 up to now) or even infinite values. These findings on the 2nd case of “multiplicative reduction” provides another counter example to the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer (BSD) conjecture besides the results in the 1st case of “good reduction” discussed earlier on in this 3rd chapter.

4. Conclusion

The main focus point in this piece of work is to reassess the validity of the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture (in short: BSD conjecture) that is formulated as follows:

$$\text{rank}(E) = \text{ord}_{s=1}L(E,s)$$

This the “normal” resp. strong version of the BSD conjecture which assumes that the rank of any given elliptic curve E should be equal to the order of zero of the same elliptic curve’s Hasse Weil L function at point $s = 1$ ²⁶

Although there exists some numerical evidence supporting this conjecture, particularly for lower ranked elliptic curves with $\text{rank} \leq 3$ (and within some given conductor ranges) ²⁷, the BSD conjecture has only been proven for some special cases (i.a. lower ranked elliptic curves as well) with some specific assumptions about the “underlying” elliptic curves ²⁸.

The main focus of this paper is not to try to build upon the work of the researchers mentioned above and prove the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture but to go to the opposite direction and try to provide some counter examples in a more analytical way by evaluating the Hasse Weil L function’s main properties (especially at the point $s = 1$) that is a very crucial part of the BSD conjecture as well. Throughout this work we will analyze the different cases for the Hasse Weil L function and its infinite Euler product representation, especially for the case of “good reduction” and “multiplicative reduction” ²⁹ which provides us with a good theoretical foundation for reassessing the validity of the BSD conjecture.

Although there exists some numerical evidence supporting this conjecture, particularly for lower ranked elliptic curves with $\text{rank} \leq 3$ (and within some given conductor ranges) ³⁰ i.a. because calculation with higher ranks is more resp. too resource intensive, the BSD conjecture has only been proven for some special cases with some specific assumptions about the “underlying” elliptic curves ³¹.

26 cf. i.a. Moser (2020)

27 cf. Cremona (2011)

28 cf. Moser (2020) and Miller (2010b) who proved the BSD conjecture for many elliptic curves of lower ranks of 0 and 1 by making additional assumptions about conductor ranges and with help of computers.

29 cf. i.a chapter 2 for the more detailed definition and explanation of the different cases that could occur for the Hasse Weil L function (for generic variable s and for $s = 1$)

30 cf. Cremona (2011)

31 cf. Moser (2020) and Miller (2010b) who proved the BSD conjecture for many elliptic curves of lower ranks of 0 and 1 by making additional assumptions about conductor ranges and with computer assistance.

The main focus of this research paper was and is not to try to extend the work the researchers mentioned above and prove the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture but to move to the opposite direction by providing some counter examples in a more analytical way by evaluating the Hasse Weil L function’s main properties (especially at the point $s = 1$). In this work we have analyzed the different cases for the Hasse Weil L function and its infinite Euler product representation, especially for the case of “good reduction” and “multiplicative reduction” and we have come to conclusion that in both cases the assumed main statement of the BSD conjecture does not hold because while the right-hand side (RHS) order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$) could be undefined for a given elliptic curve E (i.a. because the order of zero concept does not apply for non-finite values of dependent variables like e.g. the infinite number of existing prime numbers N_{primes} resp. if a function only converges to 0 (with multiplicity ≥ 1) when at least one of its dependent variables like N_{primes} need to go to infinite heights and for finite $N < N_{\text{primes}}$, no zeros could be found for both the single terms of a whole function like the infinite Euler product and the whole function itself then the order of zero is not defined resp. it is undefined for this function and the order of zero for this function is also not zero³² or any positive integer³³ and it is also not infinite³⁴), the rank of the same given elliptic curve E could never be undefined but always takes defined values of 0 or a positive finite integer or could even be infinite which provides at least 2 counter examples (good reduction case & multiplicative reduction case) to the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture that in our opinion falsely assumes that the LHS rank of any given elliptic curve E would always = the RHS that is the order of zero of the Hasse Weil L function (at $s = 1$) for any given elliptic curve E .

32 The order of zero of the infinite Euler product function is not zero, because for $N_{\text{primes}} \rightarrow \text{infinity}$, it converges to 0. And functions with zero order of zero do never reach 0.

33 The order of zero of the infinite Euler product function is also not a positive finite integer number, because no single terms of the infinite product reaches 0 for prime numbers $p \geq 2$ (only for $p = 0$ the single term of the Euler product would be equal to 0 which is impossible for prime numbers be).

34 The order of zero of the infinite Euler product function is not infinite as well, because when a function has infinite order of zero, it need have at least 1 zero of multiplicity of ≥ 1 when all dependent function variables (x , n or N resp. N_{primes}) do all take finite values that is not the case here because $N_{\text{primes}} \rightarrow \text{infinity}$ (and even if N_{primes} would hypothetically be finite, no single term of the whole infinite Euler product would reach 0 if not prime p would be equal to 0 which is never possible). Or in case of a constant function of $f(x) = c = 0$, the function value need to be zero for finite values of the dependent variable(s) (e.g. x) to have an infinite order of zero (and the function can not only be 0 when e.g. the dependent variable x do approach infinity).

Appendix

a) Derivation of the Hasse Weil L function at $s=1$ which is the formula (4) in chapter 2

We first start with the generic Hasse Weil Zeta function (1):

$$L(E, s) = \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 - a_p(p^{-s}) + p^{(1-2s)})}$$

Then we plug in $s=1$ into above Hasse Weil L function:

$$\begin{aligned} L(E, 1) &= \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 - a_p(p^{-1}) + p^{(1-2*1)})} \\ &= \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 - a_p(p^{-1}) + p^{(-1)})} \\ &= \prod_p \frac{1}{(1 + p^{(-1)}(1 - a_p))} \\ &= \prod_p \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}(1 - a_p)\right)} \end{aligned}$$

And so we get the Hasse Weil Zeta function at $s = 1$ which is equivalent to the formula (4).

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